

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND RECRUITMENT PRACTICES OF THE COMMERCIAL BANKS IN RIVERS STATE

By

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Abstract

The study investigates the influence of artificial intelligence (AI) on recruitment practices of commercial banks in Rivers State, Nigeria. The study specifically assessed how the dimensions of AI—automation and data analytics influences outsourcing and referral within the banking sector. The research adopted a cross-sectional design approach, utilizing a structured questionnaire administered recruitment officers and managers of selected commercial banks. The accessible populations comprised 495, human resource department workers, supervisors and managers of commercial banks in Rivers State. A sample of 214 respondents was determined using the Krejcie and Morgan table. Data were analysed using Spearman's Rank Order Correlation to determine the strength and direction of relationships between variables. The findings revealed a correlation between the dimension of artificial intelligence and recruitment practices. Findings revealed that automation has a strong positive relationship with both outsourcing and employee referral, while data analytics also showed significant positive correlations with outsourcing and employee referral. The study concludes that AI serves as a transformative tool for modern recruitment, enabling banks to attract and retain high-quality talent efficiently. It recommends that commercial banks should invest in AI-driven recruitment systems and analytics platforms to optimize hiring processes and strengthen their competitive advantage in the evolving financial environment.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Automation, Data Analytics, Outsourcing, Employee Referral, Recruitment Practices.

1.1 Introduction

The survival of commercial banks depends on the people they hire: The right human capital recruitment enhances the firm's ability to manage risk, satisfy their customers, create trust, comply with regulations, protect customer assets, and drive innovation in an accelerated dynamic economy. Employees are the cornerstone of every decision,

transaction, and customer experience in the banking industry. All the stakeholders in the banks jointly ascertain the operation, regulatory, and service quality performance; hence, recruitment is not an ordinary administrative task but a strategic recruitment endeavour that guarantees the alignment of workforce aptitude with institutional goals. However, poor hiring quality brings forth failures in achieving these stated goals and objectives, compliance lapses, reputation deterioration, and costly staff employee turnover (World Economic Forum, 2020). Furthermore, the increasing digitalisation, competition, and changing client taste and expectations have amplified the importance of hiring efficient, flexible, and ethical workers. This has been exemplified during the Covid-19 pandemic period, where firms with excellent recruitment practices gained a competitive advantage, customer confidence and resilience (McKinsey & Company, 2021).

Excellent recruitment practices (demanding job analysis, competency-based selection, and structured evaluation methods) are a vital tool for attracting, selecting, and retaining the right talent in commercial banks. Basing the firm's hiring processes on merit, transparency, and organised appraisal is important in banks. Where onboarding and regulatory training are expensive, engaging in the right practices will lower the employee turnover rate and improve job satisfaction among employees (CIPD, 2022). In contradiction, feeble recruitment practices can result in skill mismatches, ethical risks, and poor customer service, all of which weaken a bank's performance and credibility. The environment and global influence have made the financial sector more digitised; banks now require professionals with hybrid skills in digital finance, data analytics, cybersecurity, and customer engagement. Hence, recruiting candidates who can navigate complex technologies and deliver human-centred banking experiences to maintain compliance in complex operating environments becomes a necessity (Deloitte, 2020). Successful high-quality recruitment translates into lower recruitment costs, high productivity, and a faster learning period for new hires.

The right person must be recruited to improve the firm's efficiency and viability and maintain a culture of long-term sustainability. Getting the right person also involves following the right processes, and proactive recruitment processes include building an innovative team whose recruitment is based on merit, diversity, fairness, ethical standards and learning capabilities (PwC Nigeria, 2025). The adoption of artificial intelligence in the banks should be based on fairness and efficiency to avoid algorithmic prejudice and

maintain ethical standards that will maintain honesty and social legitimacy for the firms (PwC Nigeria, 2025; World Economic Forum, 2020). Since the banks' efficiency lies in the quality of the staff they recruit, the recruited staff should be competent, talented and have a sound behavioural attitude in carrying out their job roles to swiftly adjust to changes in the market and handle difficulties. Hence, screening with artificial intelligence must balance efficiency, fairness, openness, respect for ethical norms and avoidance of algorithmic bias (World Economic Forum, 2020).

In today's competitive financial environment, exemplary recruitment practices are a key determinant of strategic advantage and a differentiator for employer branding and talent attraction. Organisations with good hiring processes and explicit career paths and development have the tendency of recruiting the best talent who will contribute immensely in boosting productivity, performance, commitment, loyalty and trust in the organisation (McKinsey & Company, 2021; CIPD, 2022). Banks that demonstrate clear career pathways, robust selection processes, and commitment to employee development attract higher-quality applicants, retain employees longer, improve productivity, and strengthen commitment among employees, experience superior customer service, and have better financial performance (McKinsey & Company, 2021; CIPD, 2022). When a bank invests in recruitment excellence, operational stability, regulatory compliance, and sustainable competitive advantage, their performance increases, and this is essential for maintaining stability, trust, and long-term performance. Hence, understanding and improving recruitment practices in the Nigerian banking environment has become an essential concern for both scholars and practitioners in human resource management.

The use of AI offered the banking sector some opportunities in hiring through consideration of morality, legality, and fairness in recruitment processes. The adoption of AI in hiring creates a faster hiring process through automation of repetitive tasks such as résumé screening and interview scheduling, making it easier to fill vacancies much faster (Workable, 2024; Talent Business Partners, 2024). It also improved candidate matching, reduced human bias, enhanced candidate experience and enabled data-driven decision-making. Handling Large Applicant Pools – AI can efficiently process and evaluate thousands of applications, something that would be time-consuming for human recruiters.

AI usage also enhances cost efficiency, data-driven decision-making, consistency in evaluation, predictive analytics for talent retention and strategic talent acquisition.

However, inadequately built recruitment algorithms may create prejudices and unfavourable diversity outcomes if not properly managed despite their screening efficiency in choosing the right eligible candidates from broad application pools (Financial Times, 2024; McKinsey & Company, 2023). Thus, AI requires careful management to follow rules in the recruitment process and enhance algorithmic effectiveness while establishing administrative measures to protect procedural fairness and regulatory adherence. The choices the banks made in their hiring process affect their risk profiles, regulatory compliance, and efficiency in satisfying their clients. Hence, it is imperative to find a balance for efficiency in a regulated environment.

Several studies (IBM, 2024; Financial Times, 2024; Workable, 2024; McKinsey & Company, 2023; AIHR, 2023; Arxiv, 2023; Proshare, 2024; PwC Nigeria, 2025) have emphasised the importance of artificial intelligence efficiency and recruitment practices, but there is a dearth of empirical research on the influence of artificial intelligence adoption on the recruitment practices of money deposit banks in Rivers State. Hence, this study will bridge this gap by providing valuable insights on the impact of artificial intelligence adoption on the recruitment practices of the money deposit bank in Rivers State.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Continuous poor recruitment practices have often created challenging situations in the commercial institutions. Recruitment is often made based on informal methods in the form of short-term contracts, internal recommendations and nepotism instead of merit-based procedures (Ekesiba, 2024; Mohammed & Modu, 2024). Using this approach often results in the recruiting of unqualified persons and upholding informal and unstable employment connections within the banking industry (Dawodu & Okonji, 2022). Moreover, inadequate transparent, data-driven recruiting practices have led to using favouritism and poor cohesion in the recruitment process and thus weakening process trust and professional ethics (Olanipekun & Aborisade, 2019).

Poor hiring processes have become a big challenge in the banking institution, as employees hired through non-meritocratic processes often exhibit lower morale disposition, poor commitment, and higher intention to quit and turnover rates (Bamigboye & Abdulazeez, 2023). Several bank institutions now employ inaccurate job descriptions, use employee referrals or employee theft from competitors and hire temporary workers, and professional

qualifications and competencies are no longer used as basic requirements for recruitment. This poor decision has made the banks recruit staff that do not have the right skills for the job roles, resulting in inefficiency in job performance, reduced service efficiency, non-compliance with rules, procedures and requirements, and lesser job and customer satisfaction (Ekesiba, 2024). These problems have raised concern about high operating costs. Which hinders performance and reduces brand loyalty, trust and the institution's reputation and competitive advantage (Dannap, 2023).

Despite the move by the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and the Chartered Institute of Bankers of Nigeria (CIBN) to guidelines to enhance transparency and standardisation in hiring, many institutions failed to abide by these rules (Mohammed & Modu, 2024). Instead of using structured aptitude testing and psychometric evaluation, non-professional methods are used (Dawodu & Okonji, 2022); hence, the consistent occurrence of poor recruitment practices. This study aims to tackle the issue of poor recruitment services by implementing Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the recruitment processes of commercial banks in Rivers State, with the goals of creating a merit-based system, accelerating the recruitment timeline, and improving the quality of talent acquisition.

Figure 1: A conceptual framework showing the relationship between artificial intelligence and recruitment practices of commercial banks, in Rivers State

1.3 Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to examine the relationship between artificial intelligence and recruitment practices of commercial banks in Rivers State. The specific objectives are to:

- i. Explore the relationship between automation and outsourcing of the commercial banks in Rivers State
- ii. Determine the link between automation and employee referral in the commercial banks in Rivers State.
- iii. Assess the bond between data analytics and outsourcing in the commercial banks in Rivers State.
- iv. Investigate the association between data analytics and employee referral practices in the commercial banks in Rivers State.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions were given in the study:

- i. What is the association between automation and outsourcing of the commercial banks in Rivers State?
- ii. How does automation relate to employee referral practices in the commercial banks in Rivers State?
- iii. How does data analytics relate to the outsourcing of the commercial banks in Rivers State?
- iv. What is the linkage between data analytics and employee referral practices in commercial banks in Rivers State?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were stated and tested in this study.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between automation and outsourcing of the commercial banks in Rivers State.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between automation and employee referral practices in the commercial banks in Rivers State.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between data analytics and outsourcing of the commercial banks in Rivers State.

H₀₄: There is no significant relationship between data analytics and employee referral practices in the commercial banks in Rivers State.

2.1 Conceptual Review

Artificial Intelligence (AI) Adoption

The use of artificial intelligence (AI) in the organization's hiring process involves integrating machine learning, natural language processing, and predictive algorithms into the recruitment process to facilitate faster hiring decisions and manage a large volume of candidate data with transparency and accountability, thereby reducing bias, improving decision-making, and creating a more efficient hiring process (Hossain et al., 2024; Bhatia, 2021). Pillai and Sivathanu (2024) suggest that the adoption of AI in the recruiting process enhances faster processing of high-volume applicant data, assuring the meticulous choice of candidates that satisfy the job position for efficient performance. Employing AI in the commercial bank enhances compliance, reduces human bias (Sulaimon et al., 2021), and promotes data-driven talent hunts, reducing the task complication of the management and enhancing better focus on strategic tasks by the HR professionals (Nawaz et al., 2023). When artificial intelligence is integrated into work to reduce ethical oversight and compliance with the law, it boosts the firm's competitive advantage, promotes higher operational gains and fairness in recruitment practices, reduces repetition of mistakes and enhances higher compliance with the law (Mori et al., 2024; Pillai & Sivathanu, 2024).

Automation

When automation is used in the recruitment process (RC), it involves using technology to carry out distinctive, long transactions or operations, such as carrying out the processing of candidates' screening resumes and engaging in the recruitment evaluation process without human physical efforts. Automation of RC makes hiring easier, lowers administrative work and speeds up the RC process to lower the operating costs (Carolina et al., 2024). Automated workflows enhance accuracy, correctness of repetitive tasks, speed, cost reduction, reduction of bias, moral obligation, and compliance with laws and provide data-driven insights for effective staff planning.

Automation enhances effective applicant experience through personalised messages, timely news updates, and faster activity feedback loops (Verma & Garg, 2023). Automation of RC

assists HR experts in carrying out repetitive, time-consuming general tasks to enable them to focus on workforce management and strategic decisions. However, it is important to note that automation efficiency relies on human input effectiveness, and these faster automation efficiency advantages should not compromise fairness and empathy in hiring. The best approach for DMB is a hybrid model, which involves using automation for high-volume, low-risk tasks and human experts' judgement for final selection and compliance (Mori et al., 2024; Akpa, 2025). Therefore, automation is the most important part of a modern hiring system that combines speed, accuracy, and moral obligation.

Data Analytics

Data analytics in recruitment encompass orderly gathering, cleaning, transforming, and analysing and interpretation of potential employees and staff data to guide hiring decisions and predict the future personnel. An organisation, could have excellent employees, align them with the firm's culture to lower intention to leave and labour turnover risks by using advanced analytics for predictive modelling, pattern recognition, and performance data requirements (Saini & Bansal, 2024). Data analytics is a strategic intelligence system that supports hiring procedures that are fair, clear, and focused on the future. It is used for finding bias, predict future personnel shortages, assists with targeted training and retention plans and evaluate the success of recruiters to keep improving their selection techniques by looking at past hiring data. (Khan et al., 2023).

Recruitment Practices

Recruitment practices comprise organised efforts, policies and strategies for identifying, evaluating and attracting the best talents with the skills, cultural fit and experience required to achieve organisational goals. The recruitment process, from branding and sourcing talents to structured interviews and onboarding, should be based on openness, fairness, and compliance with strategic goals and objectives (Singh & Kaur, 2022). The traditional recruitment process formerly used by firms solely relied on placing advertisements and conducting interviews to pick the required talents for the organisation, but the use of artificial intelligence and other digital tools has changed this old traditional method of hunting for talents. With globalisation, modern firms now employ digital tools to enhance hiring, get the most highly skilled talent, promote diversity, and manage relationships (Agyeman et al., 2023). The effectiveness and efficiency of the recruitment processes have a direct effect on productivity, employee performance, engagement and retention. Standard

recruitment processes and procedures guarantee personnel's technical skills, behaviour, and competence in a sector requiring sound governance, trust, honesty, and accuracy for efficiency, human value, and being competitive in the long run (Goswami & Mansi, 2025; Singh & Kaur, 2022).

Outsourcing

Outsourcing in recruitment practices refers to a process of contracting recruitment of candidates to external vendors to handle the hiring services, instead of conducting it internally to enhance operational efficiency, reduce costs, and focus on core business activities where they have competencies. It is an indispensable tool for experiencing differentiated skills, reducing operational costs and enhancing flexibility and adaptability in the organization. When a firm decides to outsource their non-core tasks like IT services and human resources, it enhances more competencies and better focus on important job roles, while also enjoying the benefits of the vendor's efficiency and economies of scale (Sakib, 2023; Abdul-Halim, 2014; Yankova-Yordanova, 2021).

Referral

Referral is a hiring strategy in which existing firm staff recommend potential candidates from their personal, social or professional networks for vacant job opportunities. Referral is a popular process of attracting high-quality applicants who often exhibit better cultural fit and stronger organisational commitment (Kowske & Anthony, 2020). Using referral methods often reduced hiring time, produced higher-quality applicants, and reduced hiring costs compared to traditional hiring methods (Dhillon, 2020; Pallais & Sands, 2016). Candidates who are referred to a job role are often given better knowledge of their job from their referrer, which makes it more likely that they will fit in with the company's culture and expectations (Gode & Gaur, 2023; Bozionelos et al., 2021). Referral-based hiring supports faster onboarding and improved early job performance, which result in reduced hiring risk and improved selection accuracy.

2.2 Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) propounded by *Fred D. Davis (1989)* proposes that two key factors determine technological adoption. The factors are Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived (PU). PU is the extent of believing that using a technology will enhance individual job performance, while PEOU is the degree of believing that usage

of technology will be free from effort. These two perceptions influence a user's attitude and their behavioural intention to use the technology (Davis, 1989). The TAM framework is relevant in explaining how HR professionals, recruiters, and managers at commercial banks accept and use AI technologies in their recruitment processes, where compliance, speed, and efficiency are essential.

2.3 Empirical Review

Salemcity et al. (2025) investigate the impact of AI on cost reduction and profitability for commercial Banks (DMBs) in Nigeria. The study adopts a quantitative approach to achieve its stated objectives. Multivariate models were used. The study findings reveal that AI investments correlate with cost efficiency and profitability in Nigerian DMBs. The study found that AI-driven automation and predictive analytics improve banking operations and lower operational expenses while improving service delivery. The study emphasises the strategic value of AI in banking, proposing empirical evidence. The study suggests using AI in enhancing operational efficiency and financial performance in the banking sector.

Fiberesima (2025) explores artificial intelligence and human resource procurement in commercial banks in Rivers State. The cross-sectional survey design study's target population comprises management staff of twenty-one (21) commercial banks in Rivers State. The study was a census study. A questionnaire was used for data collection. Data were analysed using tables, simple percentages, mean score ratings, and standard deviations, and the stated hypotheses were tested using Spearman's rank correlation coefficient. The findings revealed a strong and positive relationship between artificial intelligence and measures of human resource procurement (recruitment, selection and placement). The study concludes that a relationship exists between artificial intelligence and human resource procurement in commercial banks in Rivers State. The study recommends reducing recruitment costs through adoption of artificial intelligence.

Hussaini et al. (2024) examine artificial intelligence and fraud detection of listed commercial banks in Nigeria. The survey design uses questionnaires for data collection from 14 listed commercial banks in Nigeria. The simple random sampling technique was used to select 10 banks. Regression was conducted. The result shows a positive and significant influence artificial intelligence on fraud detection among commercial banks.

3.0 Methodology

The cross-sectional survey was used in this study. The accessible populations comprise of 495 human resource employees, managers and Supervisors of 15 selected commercial banks in Rivers State. A sample of 214 respondents was derived using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table. Random sampling technique was used. The primary data was obtained using a well-structured questionnaire. Face and content validity were used to determine the validity of the instrument used in this investigation. The reliability was determined using Cronbach's Alpha. Cronbach's Alpha reliability level of 0.7 was used in the investigation. Values above 7.0 are considered composite reliable. Spearman's rank correlation were used for the analysis.

4.0 Results and Discussion

214 questionnaires were distributed, but only 202(94.4%) copies were returned, and this constitutes the valid questionnaire. The hypotheses test is undertaken at a 95.5% confidence interval, and the decision rule is state where $P < 0.05 =$ Reject the null hypotheses and where $P > 0.05 =$ Accept the null hypotheses.

Table 1: Correlations between Automation and the Dimensions of Recruitment Practices

		Automation	Outsourcing	Referral	
S p e a r m a n , s R h o	Automation	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.865**	.855**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000	.000
		N	202	202	202
	Outsourcing	Correlation Coefficient	.865**	1.000	.830**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.	.000
		N	202	202	202
	Referral	Correlation Coefficient	.855**	.830**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.
		N	202	202	202

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output, 2025.

Automation and Outsourcing : As shown in Table 1, the Spearman's rho value is 0.865 ($p = 0.000$), which is less than the significance threshold of 0.05. The coefficient of determination (r^2) is 0.748, implied that, 74.8% of the variation in outsourcing can be

explained by automation . Based on these findings, the null hypothesis (H_{01}) is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis (H_{a1}) is accepted. This indicates a strong significant and positive relationship between automation and outsourcing

Automation and Employee referral: Table 1, column 6 also reveals a Spearman’s rho value of 0.855($p = 0.000$), which is below the alpha level of 0.05. The r^2 value of 0.731 suggests that 73.1% of the variance in referral is attributable to automation. Consequently, the null hypothesis (H_{02}) is rejected in favour of the alternative hypothesis. This confirms a strong and positive relationship between automation and referral .

Table 2: Correlations between Data Analytics and the Dimension of Recruitment Practices

			Data Analytics	Outsourcing	Referral
S p e a r m a n , s r h o	Data Analytics	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.735**	.745**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000	.000
		N	202	202	202
	Outsourcing	Correlation Coefficient	.735**	1.000	.715**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.	.000
		N	202	202	202
	Referral	Correlation Coefficient	.745**	.715**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.
		N	202	202	202

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output, 2025.

Data Analytics and Outsourcing : According to Table 2, column 5, the Spearman’s rho value is 0.735 ($p = 0.000$), which is below the significance level of 0.05. The coefficient of determination (r^2) is 0.540, indicating that. 54% of the variation in outsourcing is explained by data analytics . Given this result, the null hypothesis (H_{03}) is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis (H_{a3}) is accepted. This demonstrates a strong and significant positive relationship between data analytics and outsourcing .

Data Analytics and Referral: As shown in table 2, column 6, the Spearman’s rho value is 0.745($p = 0.000$), which is less than the 0.05 significance level. The r^2 value is 0.555 indicating that data analytics accounts for 55.5% of the variation in referral . Based on this evidence, the null hypothesis (H_{04}) is rejected in favour of the alternative hypothesis. This

suggests that there is a strong significant and positive relationship between data analytics and referral .

Discussion of Findings

The study findings shows that all the dimensions of artificial intelligence (automation and data analytics), have a significant and positive relationships with recruitment practices among commercial banks in Rivers State, Nigeria.

The tested hypothesis one shows a strong and positive relationship between automation and outsourcing ($\rho = 0.865$, $p < 0.05$). The result of the r^2 (0.748) implies that approximately 74.8% of the variation in outsourcing among commercial banks can be explained by their level of automation. Thus, often, changes in recruitment practices are influenced by the automation. Engaging in automation enhances better recruitment practices by streamlining repetitive administrative tasks and improving the speed and accuracy of candidate selection. This implies that commercial banks that adopt automated recruitment systems tend to outsource efficiently. This suggests that automation reduces administrative burden, improves the speed of information processing, and enhances decision accuracy, making outsourcing more effective. The correlation analysis shows a very strong and positive relationship between automation and outsourcing ($\rho = 0.865$, $p < 0.05$), indicating that organizations that integrate automated systems into their recruitment processes tend to outsource more efficiently. This result aligns with Fibresima (2025) that artificial intelligence correlates positively with human resource procurement in commercial banks in Rivers State.

The second finding, which showed a strong relationship between automation and referral ($\rho = 0.855$, $p < 0.05$), suggests that automation correlate with employee referral. This suggests that automated recruitment platforms help banks streamline their referral processes by simplifying candidate submission, improving communication channels, and enabling efficient tracking of referred applicants. Automation also boosts participation in referral programs because employees find the process more convenient and transparent. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected, confirming that automation significantly improves the effectiveness and responsiveness of employee referral practices in commercial banks. This conform with Hussaini et al. (2024) that that automation enhances the quality of hiring outcomes by improving precision and efficiency in talent identification. and also relates with fraud detection.

Moreover, the results demonstrated that data analytics is significantly and positively related to outsourcing ($\rho = 0.735, p < 0.05$). This means that data analytics plays a crucial role in guiding outsourcing decisions by providing insights on vendor performance, service quality, operational cost analysis, and workload patterns. When banks utilize analytical tools, they make more informed outsourcing decisions that enhance efficiency and reduce operational risks. Since the null hypothesis is rejected, the findings confirm that data analytics is a key determinant of the outsourcing strategies used by commercial banks in the state. This finding is consistent with Salemcity et al. (2025) that use of AI has significant positive correlation human resource management practices..

Lastly, the strong positive correlation between data analytics and referral ($\rho = 0.745, p < 0.05$) reinforces the assertion that the effective use of analytical tools in recruitment enables organizations to make more informed and objective hiring decisions, thereby improving the overall quality of employees selected. This outcome suggests that data analytics enhances the referral system by helping banks identify suitable candidates, predict employee-job fit, and monitor referral outcomes. Analytical tools allow recruiters to evaluate the quality and success rate of referred applicants, thereby improving the efficiency of referral-based recruitment. The rejection of the null hypothesis confirms that data analytics contributes meaningfully to the effectiveness and quality of employee referral processes in commercial banks. This conform with Tambaetal, (2019) that aartificial intelligence correlates with human resource practices.

5.0 Conclusion

This study investigated the impact of automation and data analytics on recruitment practices, particularly outsourcing and employee referral, within commercial banks in Rivers State. The empirical findings substantiate that both automation and data analytics markedly improve recruitment efficiency and strategic decision-making. Automation was found to have a very strong and positive relationship with both outsourcing and employee referral. This means that automated systems make the hiring process easier, cut down on paperwork, make hiring decisions faster and more clear, and make hiring decisions more accurate. These results show how important automation is for modernising the way banks hire people.

The study also found that data analytics has a strong and important positive link to

outsourcing and referrals. This shows that banks can make smart outsourcing decisions and improve the quality of hiring based on referrals by using analytical tools. Banks can use data insights to better judge how well vendors are doing, predict how many employees they will need, find the best candidates, and improve their hiring results. In general, the results confirm that digital transformation, which includes automation and data analytics, is necessary for commercial banks to improve their recruitment effectiveness, operational efficiency, and competitive edge. The study concludes that commercial banks should persist in investing in advanced technological tools to enhance their recruitment systems and facilitate long-term organisational success.

6.0 Recommendations

1. Banks should automate repetitive and non-core HR tasks to free up time and resources that can be strategically redirected to evaluate and manage outsourcing partnerships.
2. Banks should use automated referral platforms that make it easy for employees to send, track, and keep an eye on the progress of the candidates they refer.
3. Banks should set up data-driven outsourcing frameworks to help them figure out trends in workload, productivity, and operational gaps that need outsourcing.
4. HR should make referral dashboards to help them see the results of referrals, the flow of candidates, and any problems that are slowing things down so they can make better decisions.

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